

The Potapenco Spine Therapy® (PST) approach in the physical recovery of patients with Lumbar Discopathy, using PRQ Questionnaire

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.1384033](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1384033)

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Key words: lumbar discopathy, PRQ, back pain, discus degeneration, manual therapy, kinetotherapy

Abstract

Back pain caused by Lumbar Discopathy is caused by the natural aging process, which leads to dehydration and deterioration of the intervertebral discs. Other risk factors include repetitive physical exertion (such as lifting weights), being sedentary, and trauma (eg, a fall or car accident). As symptoms, people with lumbar discopathy may experience low back pain, discomfort and stiffness. Sometimes, this condition can lead to lumbar radiculopathy, which manifests as pain in the leg and antero-lateral part of the thigh⁽¹⁾. International literature tells us that treatment can include physical therapy, pain medication and, in severe cases, surgery. In this work, we aimed to analyze 3 specific cases that will be treated through Potapenco Spine Therapy® (PST), a Manual Therapy concept specialized in the physical recovery of back pain. We will try the effectiveness of this approach in the case of patients with chronic Lumbar Discopathy.

Introduction

In the realm of research, the single case study has been recognized as a valuable tool for sharing insights, demonstrating new concepts, discovering novel phenomena, consolidating hypotheses, and sparking original ideas⁽²⁾. Case studies play a crucial role in training future health professionals. Case studies give students and young professionals the opportunity to deal with real and complex healthcare situations. By analyzing a specific case, doctors, medical assistants or public health specialists learn to apply theoretical knowledge in the practical context. These cases can cover a wide range of issues, from diagnosis and treatment, to ethics, communication with patients and resource management. Case studies are a valuable tool in training future health professionals⁽³⁾. Regarding annual international statistics specific to lumbar discopathy, we could not find accurate data in open sources until October 2023. However, it is important to know that this condition affects a significant proportion of the adult population and that proper prevention and management are essential for maintaining spine health.

Methods and results

Clinical results from the cases provided in this narrative report suggest that treating Lumbar Discopathy patients with Potapenco Spine Therapy® (PST) resulted in immediate and long-term therapeutic benefit as reported by the patients.

Conclusion

This study offers the possibility of measuring and objectifying the effectiveness of the treatment carried out, based on the Potapenco Spine Therapy® (PST) approach in patients who complain of chronic back pain and who have

been diagnosed with Lumbar Discopathy, the quantification of the measurement being organized based on the use of the specialized PRQ questionnaire.

Introduction

Most studies in this direction suggest that Pain and Discomfort are caused by a degenerative disc. It can result in a loss of vertebral body height and undue strain on the failing disc, which can produce symptoms including tingling, numbness, and weakness in the hands and arms. This is usually caused by the disc material degenerating. If the sickness is asymptomatic, imaging tests like magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and X-rays can be used to diagnose it ⁽⁴⁾. The most commonly affected level of disc degeneration in both men and women is the L4/5 level ⁽⁵⁾. Specifically, discogenic back pain (DBP) is a subcategory of back pain defined as pain due to pathology of the disc. Despite the absence of radiographic evidence of disc herniation compressing the spinal column or nerves, the pain in DBP is multifactorial and mainly stems from the degeneration of the intervertebral disc but is also thought to be a result of biomechanical instability, localized inflammation, vertebral endplate pathology, and reinnervation of the area with nociceptive, unmyelinated nerve fibers ⁽⁶⁾. With all this information that exists in specialized literature, we can find many controversial studies that prove to us that the high level of pain suffered by the patient does not always speak of pronounced degenerative processes based on the screening performed, and vice versa. It is known that, DBP primarily results after years of pathologic disc degeneration. Within DBP, there are two types of degeneration, a physiologic degeneration of the disc with absence of back pain, and a pathologic form of disc degeneration known as degenerative disc disease (DDD). It was previously was thought that years of repetitive movement and weight bearing were the main cause of DDD; however, a historical cohort study comparing competitive athletes to control subjects demonstrated greater disc degeneration in the lumbar spine of athletes; interestingly, there was less associated back pain in the athlete group than the control group ⁽⁷⁾.

The treatment of these cases is diverse, based on the international specialized literature, we can say, as an example, in USA, it is estimated that more than \$90 miliard dollars is spent annually on the diagnosis and treatment of LBP ^(8,9). In 2015, the Global Spine Care Initiative reported LBP to be the fourth leading cause of disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) globally ⁽¹⁰⁾. It is estimated that one in three people report having LBP, and the lifetime prevalence ranges from 60-80% of the population ⁽¹¹⁾. Adding to the existing burden, the prevalence of LBP has been growing exponentially over the past few decades ⁽¹²⁾.

With the aim of improving the quality of life of these patients, reducing pain and qualitatively returning to the daily activities of these patients, my colleagues and I, in recent years, very actively implement the new therapeutic approaches in the field of Medical Physical Rehabilitation through the combination of the multiple concepts of Kinetotherapy and Manual Therapy ^(13,14,15,16,17). For a better quantification of these processes, a new tool for measuring the dynamic state of the patient was developed and implemented, which was patented and named as PRQ[®] (Potapenco Roman Questionnaire) ^(18,19,20). We propose as the aim of this study a practical clinical investigation with the hypothesis that the conceptual approach of Potapenco Spine Therapy[®] (PST) can be useful in the treatment of patients who complain of back pain following degenerative diseases of the intervertebral disc of the spine. We want to quantify the results obtained from the procedures performed and subject to the systematization of this type of patients suffering from different types of back ailments, especially the pathologies related to the intervertebral disc and the associated myofascial syndrome.

Method and results

In all 3 cases reported below, as **Exclusion Criteria** for this patients, before reaching us, were diagnosed by the Neurologist with Lumbar Discopathy and Paravertebral Myofascial Syndrome, and during the MRI investigation, disc herniation was not diagnosed, but it was diagnosed moderate degeneration of the L4-L5 intervertebral disc with bulging on the left wide base up to 4 millimeters. As a common factor, all these 3 patients previously followed different types of drug treatments, Chiropractic and Osteopathy procedures, which unfortunately did not give results. In such a case, no medication was prescribed as treatment, but a medical physical recovery was recommended by the Neurologist, with referral to us at the

Clinic. In the Physical Rehabilitation process, we have used a new special approach of Manual Therapy based on the concept of Potapenco Spine Therapy® (PST) and followed by a set of techniques and exercises individualized by Kinetotherapy for each individual patient, exercises followed in home conditions, which they were performed twice a day in the morning and in the evening, which lasted at least a month after the procedures were finished (patients perform them daily to this day). The duration of the exercises performed at home lasted between 20-30 minutes. The set is composed of 12 specially designed individualized exercises. All 3 patients followed (apart from Saturdays and Sundays) a course of daily specialized Manual Therapy procedures - the PST® Concept (Potapenco Spine Therapy®), procedures that lasted on average between 50-60 minutes - the procedure. At the beginning of the treatment course and at the end of the course, the patients independently completed the PRQ® Questionnaire, the same questionnaire was also completed over 3 months, which allowed highlighting the dynamic state of the patients in the study. Likewise, patients were asked to identify their pain threshold on the Numerical Pain Rating Scale from 0 to 10 and were asked to complete the Finger-to-toe Test physical test (we anticipate that all 3 could not touch each other when bending with the toes of the phalanges). Similarly, the patients were asked to subjectively describe their emotional state (of depression) from 0...10, 0 being its absence and 10 being an impossible maximum (equivalent to the state or thoughts of suicide). In the case of sleep, the scale was reversed, we asked the patients to tell us subjectively how they perceive the quality of their sleep, where 10 is the best score and tells us about an ideal sleep and 0 being a sleep of the worst quality (total insomnia).

1st Case

Male, 38 years old, until he came to us, he suffered from chronic back pain for the last 4-5 years, more acute than usual for the last 4 months, symptomatic manifested by strong back pain associated with pain and discomfort in the hip and the left leg (up to the talo-crural joint). Importantly, in the last 2 years, he used drug treatments prescribed by different doctors, which did not work. Also in these last 2 years, he used chiropractic and osteopathy services, performed by different specialists, after which he had no effect. Social history tells us about sedentary work in a commercial bank where he has been working for more than 10 years. In the last 2-3 years, he has been practicing regularly in the gym, with a personal trainer, with the aim of maintaining his athletic form and, most importantly, with the aim of reducing back discomfort. He feels depressed. Poor quality sleep.

✓ **Before to the beginning** of the Specialized Manual Therapy Procedures - the PST Concept, the patient had the following results indicated by him:

Finger to Toe Test - Negative (couldn't bend down and touch toes) measuring distance **being 11cm**.

Numerical Pain Rating Scale – **8.5 points**

PRQ Questionnaire – **71 points** (number of accumulated complaints)

Depression (8/10)

Sleep (4/10)

✓ **After Completing the Cure of 10 Specialized Manual Therapy Procedures - The PST Concept** the patient had the following results indicated by him:

Finger to Toe Test – Positive (the patient **was able to bend down** and touch the toes **without any pain** or discomfort in the back or legs) the measurement distance being +2 cm (the patient bent down below the level of the toes) .

Numerical Pain Rating Scale – **1.5 points**

PRQ Questionnaire – **7 points** (the number of complainers who still feel)

Depression (2/10)

Sleep (7/10)

✓ **The patient after 3 Months** after Completing the Cure of 10 Specialized Manual Therapy Procedures - The PST Concept in which he followed the daily execution of the Individualized Set of Kinetotherapy Exercises at home, the patient had the following results indicated by him:

Finger to Toe Test – Positive (the patient **was able to bend down** and touch the toes **without any pain** or discomfort in the back or legs) the measurement distance being +4 cm (the patient bent down below the level of the toes) .

Numerical Pain Rating Scale – 0 points

PRQ Questionnaire – 3 points (it is still felt in these questions indicated in the questionnaire)

Depression (0/10)

Sleep (8/10)

2nd Case

Male, 41 years old, Until he came to us, he had been suffering from chronic back pain for the past 7 years, more acute than usual for the past 11 months, manifested by severe back pain associated with pain and discomfort in the pelvis and left leg (up to the talo-crural joint). Importantly, in the last 2 years, he used drug treatments prescribed by different doctors, which did not work. Also in these last 2 years, he used chiropractic and osteopathy services, performed by different specialists, after which he had no effect, due to counter procedures that awakened a greater acuity. Social history tells us about sedentary work in an IT office where he has been active for more than 15 years. In the last 5 years, he has been practicing regularly in the gym, with a personal trainer, with the aim of maintaining his athletic form and, most importantly, with the aim of reducing back discomfort. For 7 months, he has not been working in the gym because of the alleged pains. He feels depressed. Poor quality sleep.

✓ **Before the beginning of the Specialized Manual Therapy Procedures - the PST Concept**, the patient had the following results indicated by him:

Finger to Toe Test - Negative (couldn't bend over and touch toes) measuring distance being 16cm.

Numerical Pain Rating Scale – 8.5 points

PRQ Questionnaire – 70 points (number of accumulated complaints)

Depression (8/10)

Sleep (5/10)

✓ **After Completing the Cure of 10 Specialized Manual Therapy Procedures - The PST Concept** the patient had the following results indicated by him:

Finger to Toe Test – Positive (the patient **was able to bend down** and touch the toes **without any pain** or discomfort in the back or legs) the measurement distance being +1 cm (the patient bent down below the level of the toes) .

Numerical Pain Rating Scale – 1 point

PRQ Questionnaire – 7 points (number of complainers still feeling)

Depression (3/10)

Sleep (8/10)

✓ **The patient after 3 Months after Completing the Cure of 10 Specialized Manual Therapy Procedures - The PST Concept** in which he followed the daily execution of the Individualized Set of Kinetotherapy Exercises at home, the patient had the following results indicated by him:

Finger to Toe Test – Positive (the patient **was able to bend down** and touch the toes **without any pain or discomfort** in the back or legs) the measurement distance being +2 cm (the patient bent down below the level of the toes) .

Numerical Pain Rating Scale – 0 points

PRQ Questionnaire – 2 points (it is still felt in these questions indicated in the questionnaire)

Depression (0/10)

Sleep (9/10)

3rd Case

Male, 39 years old, Until he came to us, he suffered from chronic back pain for the last 5 years, more acute than usual for the last 3 months, which manifested itself in severe back pain associated with pain and discomfort in the legs and left leg (up to the talo-crural joint). Importantly, in the last 2 years, he used drug treatments prescribed by different doctors, which did not work. Also in these last 2 years, he resorted to Chiropractic and Osteopathy services, performed by different specialists, after which he had no expected effect. Social history tells us about sedentary work in a Call Center office where he has been active for more than 12 years. In the last 7-8 years, he has been practicing regularly in the gym, with a personal trainer, with the aim of maintaining his athletic form and, most importantly, with the aim of

reducing back discomfort. He hasn't been to the gym for 1 month because of the alleged pains. He feels depressed. Poor quality sleep.

✓ **Before to the beginning of the Specialized Manual Therapy Procedures - the PST Concept**, the patient had the following results indicated by him:

Finger to Toe Test - Negative (couldn't bend over and touch toes) measuring distance being 6cm.

Numerical Pain Rating Scale – 9 points

PRQ Questionnaire – 71 points (number of accumulated complaints)

Depression (6/10)

Sleep (8/10)

✓ **After Completing the Cure of 10 Specialized Manual Therapy Procedures - The PST Concept** the patient had the following results indicated by him:

Finger to Toe Test – Positive (the patient **was able to bend down** and touch the toes without any pain or discomfort in the back or legs) the **measurement distance being +1 cm** (the patient bent down below the level of the toes) .

Numerical Pain Rating Scale – 1 point

PRQ Questionnaire – 7 points (number of complainers still feeling)

Depression (2/10)

Sleep (8/10)

✓ **The patient after 3 Months after Completing the Cure of 10 Specialized Manual Therapy Procedures - the PST Concept** in which he followed the daily execution of the Individualized Set of Kinetotherapy Exercises at home, the patient had the following results indicated by him:

Finger to Toe Test – Positive (the patient **was able to bend down** and touch the toes without any pain or discomfort in the back or legs) the **measurement distance being +3 cm** (the patient bent down below the level of the toes) .

Numerical Pain Rating Scale – 0 points

PRQ Questionnaire – 2 points (it is still felt in these questions indicated in the questionnaire)

Depression (0/10)

Sleep (9/10)

Discussion

From the First International Congress " Medical Forum of Physical Rehabilitation Chisinau" which took place in 2019 in the Republic of Moldova, like other international colleagues, I personally proposed an individualized treatment of Manual Therapy and Kinesiotherapy, with my own methodology developed by me the last 15 years in treating patients with different types of back pain. At that time the methodology did not have a name. In this context, being an interesting idea, we trying to develop it, with each Congress and Conference organized by the Professional Association of Kinetotherapists and Manual Therapists "Medkinetica" from the Republic of Moldova, different professional groups worked and focused on the study of different approaches to the recovery of specific and non-specific back pain. A lot of attention is focused on degenerative pathologies of the intervertebral disc and associated myofascial syndromes. The methodology proposed by me, due to the large number of cases treated and the multitude of cases with a positive effect, allowed us to develop a program (or more correctly to sy an individualized concept) for the different type of pathologies, which is now known as PST[®] (Potapenco Spine Therapy[®]) being a direction of Manual Therapy combined with Techniques and Maneuvers from Kinetotherapy. This new approach allows for the successful recovery of various conditions and complaints caused by spine ailments, especially ailments related to the degeneration of the intervertebral disc and the symptoms caused by this process. The individualization of each case allows us to choose a more effective recovery tactic and strategy that demonstrates immediate effectiveness and long-lasting positive effects, if the patient strictly complies with the recommendations made by the therapist. All 3 cases demonstrated very good results in the near term and during the following months. The PST[®] concept, approached individually for each case, leads to the expected results and allows patients to restore their physical and emotional well-being. Patients mentioned the immediate effect of the procedures and were very satisfied

with the results obtained. As a result, we will try to monitor these patients during the following months to further quantify the dynamics.

Conclusion

These cases were investigated in a clinical practice with the hypothesis that Potapenco Spine Therapy® (PST®) is a concept that can be useful in the treatment of patients who complain of back pain following degenerative diseases of the intervertebral disc of the spine. At the international level, the systems already formed for the treatment of these conditions often do not lead to the expected results in time and turn into a serious financial burden for the patient and the medical system. The interaction and mix between Manual and Kinetic maneuvers, based on studies and research, can form new useful approaches in the treatment of patients with Lumbar Discopathy and Myofascial Syndromes. This is the first report in the literature to suggest that PST® is a highly effective Manual Therapy concept. The correct combination of maneuvers and individualized methods of Kinetotherapy and Manual Therapy, performed by well-trained specialists, can have a very beneficial effect on patients suffering from back pain, even in long-term chronic cases. The immediate improvement of symptoms obtained in cases of recovery focused on the concept of PST® suggests to us that there may be a common mechanism based on (or linking) fascia, myofascial induction and degenerative dystrophic processes at the level of the intervertebral disc. As the field of Physical Rehabilitation through Kinetotherapy and Manual Therapy expands its research perspectives, future studies are needed to validate both the results obtained in the recovery process and the central strategic role that the individualized approach plays in the medical physical rehabilitation process. of different types of back pain.

Conflict of interest

Nothing to declare

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